

CONFLICT AS A CENTRAL CATEGORY OF DRAMATIC POETICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20554322>

***Abstract.** The article examines dramatic conflict as a central category of dramatic poetics in its historical-literary and structural-typological dimensions. Using a historical-theoretical and typological approach, it traces the development of the concept from Aristotle and Hegel to Russian literary theory and contemporary postdramatic theatre. The article systematises major forms of dramatic conflict according to source, degree of resolvability, and dramatic form. It argues that classical conflict theory should be expanded by the category of deconstructed conflict, where the absence or dismantling of conflict becomes an artistic principle.*

***Keywords:** dramatic conflict, collision, dramatic poetics, typology of conflict, theory of drama, Russian dramaturgy, postdramatic theatre.*

1. Introduction

The question of the nature of dramatic conflict is one of the most fundamental in literary theory. Conflict is traditionally regarded as the contradiction that generates action, organises the system of characters, and determines both the genre nature and the semantic structure of a dramatic work. Yet, despite centuries of scholarly investigation, the concept of conflict in dramatic theory remains contested: different scholarly traditions diverge in their definitions, classifications, and assessments of its role within the structure of a work.

The relevance of this article lies in the need to clarify the structural role of conflict not only in classical drama but also in modern and postdramatic forms, where the traditional model of a resolved opposition becomes insufficient. The purpose of the article is to systematise theoretical approaches to dramatic conflict and to propose a structurally clearer typology that includes both classical and contemporary forms of conflict.

To achieve this purpose, the article addresses three tasks: first, to outline the historical formation of the concept of dramatic conflict; second, to describe its development in Russian literary theory; and third, to classify the main types of conflict according to their source, degree of resolvability, and dramatic form.

2. Methodology and Analytical Framework

The article is based on historical-theoretical and structural-typological analysis. The historical-theoretical approach is used to trace the development of the concept of dramatic conflict from classical poetics to twentieth- and twenty-first-century drama theory. The structural-typological approach is used to classify forms of conflict according to their function within dramatic action.

The analytical material consists of foundational works in the theory of drama, including Aristotle, Hegel, Belinsky, Khalizev, Kostelyanets, Karyagin, Anikst, Lehmann, and studies of new Russian drama. The main criteria for classification are: the source of conflict, its location within the dramatic structure, its degree of resolvability, and the extent to which the classical conflict model is preserved or dismantled.

3. Historical Formation of the Concept of Dramatic Conflict

The theoretical conceptualisation of what would later be called 'dramatic conflict' traces back to Aristotle's *Poetics*. Aristotle does not employ the term 'conflict' itself; however, his concept of mimesis—the imitation of action—presupposes contradiction as a necessary condition of dramatic movement. *Peripeteia*, or sudden reversal into the opposite, and *anagnorisis*, or recognition, are possible only where some initial opposition of forces exists [2].

The concept of conflict in its proper terminological sense was introduced and theoretically elaborated by Hegel. In *Aesthetics*, the philosopher formulates the concept of collision (Ger. *Kollision*), understood as the clash of 'substantial forces' (*Substantialmächte*), each embodying a specific ethical principle [4]. Two aspects of the Hegelian conception are especially important. First, both substantial principles possess independent value: in dramatic conflict there is no absolutely right and no absolutely guilty side. Second, conflict within this conception necessarily implies resolution: 'eternal justice' is restored through the destruction or retreat of one of the parties. This proposition shaped the theoretical norm for understanding dramatic conflict for a full century.

In Russian aesthetic thought, the Hegelian conception was received and adapted primarily by V. G. Belinsky. In his essay 'On the Division of Poetry into Genera and Species' (1841), Belinsky defined drama as the depiction of 'living action' grounded in the struggle of opposing principles—the hero's will against external necessity, or the wills of two heroes [3]. However, Belinsky shifted the emphasis from metaphysical substantial forces to the social-psychological dimension, which later determined the specific character of the Russian tradition of conflict analysis.

4. Russian Theoretical Approaches to Dramatic Conflict

The systematic scholarly development of a theory of dramatic conflict in Russian literary studies began in the second half of the twentieth century. The works of V. E. Khalizev, B. O. Kostelyanets, and A. A. Karyagin played a decisive role in this process.

V. E. Khalizev, in *Drama as a Literary Genre* (1986), defines conflict as 'the contradiction between characters, or between a character and circumstances, that forms the core of dramatic action.' The scholar stresses that conflictuality is 'a universal property of human existence' and that it constitutes the substantive core of dramaturgy [9]. Particularly significant is Khalizev's thesis on the historicity of conflict: its nature changes from epoch to epoch, and the classical bipolar conflict represents only one of the historically possible forms.

B. O. Kostelyanets, in *Lectures on the Theory of Drama*, develops the concept of conflict in its relation to the category of action [6]. For Kostelyanets, conflict not only precedes action as its cause but is also its internal structure: conflict unfolds in every act of collision between wills. This makes it possible to view conflict not statically, as the opposition of two parties, but dynamically, as a continuous process.

A. A. Karyagin, in *Drama as an Aesthetic Problem* (1971), draws particular attention to the aesthetic function of conflict. It is through contradiction and its resolution, or non-resolution, that drama exerts its effect upon the spectator [5]. Karyagin was among the first in Russian scholarship to raise the question of fundamentally irresolvable conflicts as an independent type that does not fit the Hegelian schema.

A substantial contribution to the study of conflict was made by A. A. Anikst, who traced the evolution of dramatic theory in Russia [1]. V. A. Sakhnovskiy-Pankeev proposed a classification of conflicts according to their source and structure, distinguishing conflicts of 'man

vs. environment,' 'man vs. man,' and 'man vs. himself.' This classification anticipated later typologies.

5. Typology of Dramatic Conflict

The typology of dramatic conflict may be organised according to three structural criteria: the source of conflict, the degree of resolvability, and the transformation of conflict in modern and postdramatic forms. This division makes the classification more systematic and prevents the mixing of different typological principles.

5.1. Conflict according to source

External conflict is the opposition of a character to the environment, or of two characters embodying different social, ethical, or ideological principles. This is the most legible type of conflict and is characteristic of classical dramaturgy. Examples include Katerina vs. Kabanova in Ostrovsky's *The Storm* and Chatsky vs. Famusov's society in Griboyedov's *Woe from Wit*.

Internal, or psychological, conflict is a contradiction within the character: between desires and capacities, between an ideal self-image and actual behaviour, or between consciousness and the unconscious.

This type becomes dominant in the dramaturgy of the second half of the twentieth century. Examples include Zilov in Vampilov's *Duck Hunting* and the characters of Grishkovets.

Existential conflict is a contradiction between the human being and the very nature of existence: time, death, the meaninglessness of life, or the impossibility of genuine communication. This type is present in embryonic form already in Chekhov's *Three Sisters*, where the desire to live a 'real life' remains fundamentally unattainable, and it develops further in the postdramatic tradition.

5.2. Conflict according to degree of resolvability

Resolvable conflict is a conflict that is resolved in the finale: one side triumphs, perishes, or yields. The denouement is unambiguous and concludes the conflict. This model is characteristic of classical dramaturgy.

Irresolvable conflict is a conflict that by its nature admits of no final resolution, especially in cases of existential contradiction or conflict with insurmountable circumstances. The finale does not resolve the contradiction but merely interrupts its unfolding. This form is characteristic of the Chekhovian and post-Chekhovian tradition.

Open conflict is a conflict whose final status is deliberately left undefined by the author. The work ends, but the question of a winner or the meaning of the opposition remains open, offering the spectator or reader space for interpretation. This type is particularly characteristic of late Ostrovsky, including *The Dowerless Girl*, as well as Chekhov and new drama.

5.3. Conflict according to dramatic form

The typology developed above reflects the historically established understanding of conflict as a necessary condition of drama.

However, the theatrical and dramaturgical practice of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries calls this condition into question. According to H.-T. Lehmann, postdramatic theatre is characterised by a departure from the logic of drama as a sequence of causally linked events [7]. This implies, among other things, the weakening or abandonment of conflict as the driving force of action.

Therefore, the typology should be extended by a fourth form: deconstructed conflict. This is the deliberate dismantling of the conflict structure, in which the absence, weakening, or impossibility of classical conflict becomes an artistic statement.

Table 1. Structural typology of dramatic conflict

Criterion	Type of conflict	Main feature	Representative tendency
Source	External	Opposition between character and environment or another character	Classical dramaturgy
Source	Internal / psychological	Contradiction inside the character	Modern psychological drama
Source	Existential	Conflict between human existence and time, death, meaninglessness, or communication	Chekhovian and postdramatic tradition
Resolvability	Resolvable	Clear finale and completed opposition	Classical drama
Resolvability	Irresolvable	Contradiction cannot be finally removed	Chekhovian and post-Chekhovian drama
Resolvability	Open	Final meaning remains undefined	Late Ostrovsky, Chekhov, new drama
Dramatic form	Deconstructed	Conflict structure is dismantled or becomes impossible	Postdramatic theatre and new Russian drama

6. Discussion: Conflict in Postdramatic and New Russian Drama

In the new Russian drama of the turn of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries, represented by V. Sigarev, I. Vyrypaev, and Y. Grishkovets, conflict is not merely transformed but subjected to dismantling [8]. In Vyrypaev, the place of conflict is often taken by monologic meditation; in Grishkovets, conflict may appear as a confrontation with one's own memory and identity, without an external opponent and without possible resolution.

This does not mean that conflict disappears altogether. Rather, it migrates to another level: conflict becomes the very impossibility of classical conflict. For this reason, the category of deconstructed conflict is necessary for describing modern forms of drama that no longer rely on the classical model of causal action and final resolution.

7. Conclusion

Dramatic conflict remains one of the key categories of dramatic poetics, but its theoretical interpretation has changed significantly across historical periods. In classical theory, from Aristotle to Hegel and Belinsky, conflict is connected with action, collision, and resolution. In Russian literary theory, especially in the works of Khalizev, Kostelyanets, and Karyagin, conflict is understood more dynamically, as a historically variable and aesthetically productive structure.

The structural typology proposed in this article distinguishes conflict according to source, degree of resolvability, and dramatic form. This makes it possible to include external, internal, existential, resolvable, irresolvable, open, and deconstructed conflict within one analytical system. The inclusion of deconstructed conflict is especially important because postdramatic theatre and

new Russian drama demonstrate that the absence or dismantling of conflict can itself function as a meaningful artistic strategy.

Thus, conflict should not be understood only as a fixed opposition between two forces. It should be viewed as a flexible poetic category that may organise dramatic action, reveal psychological or existential contradiction, remain unresolved, or even be deliberately dismantled in contemporary theatrical practice.

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